

EXPLORING SCAFFOLDING TECHNIQUES FOR LISTENING SKILL DEVELOPMENT: AN ACTION RESEARCH STUDY IN VIRTUAL TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

English is recognized as the standard language for communication in most parts of the world, and is utilized as a medium of instructions in Pakistan as well; therefore, it is taught as a mandatory subject in Pakistan at all levels of education. While teaching language, reading and writing are considered literary or academic skills, whereas, listening and speaking are oral skills that are mostly learned in a natural setting. However, learners do not get enough opportunities to practice oral skills in ESL/EFL contexts. Due to this reason, they usually lack fluent communication. The present study was qualitative in nature which employed action research design to understand the impact of scaffolding technique while teaching listening skills in virtual class. Primarily, the focus of this study were struggling learners, including one female and two male students and the teacher as a participant observer. The data was collected from written feedback provided by students and teacher's observations were recorded in a researcher diary after every session. Students' feedback was analysed thematically. In addition, the researcher's diary also helped understand underlying perceptions of a teacher with scaffolding technique. The findings of the study revealed that teacher scaffolding is impactful, especially with struggling learners.

Keywords: Scaffolding, listening skills, virtual teaching, ESL, EFL.

INTRODUCTION

Listening is one of the important skills in the communication process (Stepanoviene, 2012). Ahmad and Rao (2012) pointed out that one needs to be efficient in listening to access its professional and social life. In addition to that, it is also asserted that one must have good listening skills in order to fulfil its academic role (Babae, 2017). Therefore, listening has been included in the English syllabus since Benazir Bhutto implemented English as a core subject in Primary classes (Shamim, 2008). However, teachers are either reluctant towards teaching listening or they do not have knowledge about teaching listening skills in particular (Azizulloev, 2000). Hence,

when students experience it in real-life situations, they fail to fulfil their tasks.

Being a language teacher, listening is considered an important skill to be taught. Unfortunately, teachers were hesitant to help students due to the limited audio-visual resources and unavailability of administrative support at public universities. Due to Covid-19 pandemic, virtual teaching was implemented around the world. In that case, a number of resources emerged to overcome the restrictions in teaching listening, so, teaching listening skills got convenient.

Eng et al. (2013) conducted research to assess listening competency of secondary school learners

in Pakistan. Data were collected from four-hundred and forty students from both private and public schools. The findings revealed significant differences in listening competency of urban and rural school students because the students from urban schools experienced listening even outside the classroom, so they were able to perform better. However, the students from rural schools only get a chance to listen to English in the classroom setting, so they could not comprehend the content for their real-life tasks. Therefore, the scholars decided to work more closely with struggling learners in this study, so that, when they experience listening as a part of their job, they must also be able to handle it as efficiently as others.

Emerging from Vygotsky (1987), the concept of Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) is a technique of scaffolding. It was defined as the assistance from teachers and society to become skilful (Wood et al., 1976). From the last decade, it has been enhanced in the domain of collaborative learning with peers as well (Crook, 1994). Recently, it has further expanded, including the internet resources and online software (Hughes, 2013). Thus, the purpose of this study was to explore the impact of scaffolding techniques for teaching listening strategies to developing learners through online teaching in Pakistani context.

1.0 Aim of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine the impact of teacher scaffolding for developing listening skills in online teaching. In the last few years, the researchers have integrated numerous strategies of listening both in terms of macro, micro, cognitive and metacognitive skills (Goh, 2000; Graham, 2006; Vandergrift, & Tafaghodtari, 2010). However, the use of scaffolding techniques is not observed commonly. Scaffolding technique can work on the whole group as well, but the present study focused on the low-achievers only, who lack basic skills and needed scaffolding.

2.0 Objectives of the Study

The main objectives for conducting this study were to:

- Understand the process of scaffolding technique for teaching listening skills to weak/struggling learners.

- Analyse the impact of teacher scaffolding for teaching listening skills to weak/struggling learners.

3.0 Research Questions

This study aims to answer the following research questions:

1. How can a teacher scaffold listening strategies to struggling learners in developing listening skills in online learning?
2. What are the perceptions of students after implementing the scaffolding techniques to teach listening skills to ESL/EFL students?

4.0 Literature Review

4.1 Listening Comprehension Skills

Listening and speaking skills are usually learned in the target language environment in ESL/EFL contexts. Unfortunately, students do not get many opportunities to experience listening and speaking in the target language in local contexts. Alam and Bashiruddin (2013) argued that lack of real-life language use opportunities affects learners' overall proficiency in oral communication skills. Kok (2017) explored the relationship between listening strategy use and listening proficiency with forty-four Turkish undergraduate students including thirty-seven females and seven males. The analysis of data revealed positive correlation between the level of listening comprehension strategy use and listening proficiency of the learners.

Similarly, Fathi and Hamidizadeh (2019) conducted a study in Iran on the contribution of listening strategies in second language listening proficiency, where fifty-two students were divided into experimental and control groups. The scholars observed that the use of listening strategies was useful in ESL/EFL context to improve the comprehension of learners.

In contrast, Bozorgian and Pillay (2013) investigated listening comprehension by integrating the first language in listening class. Sixty lower-intermediate female students participated in the experimental quantitative study in Iran. With one group, the listening strategies were followed using L1, meanwhile, the same listening strategies by the same teacher were used in L2 with the other group. The experimental group outperformed the control group. In brief, the results of the study indicated that L1 should be considered in the beginning if

the students are low-proficient in the target language.

4.2 Scaffolding in Online Teaching

Wertsch (1979) has defined scaffolding as an interactive inter-psychological procedure by which learners acquire knowledge while interacting with experts or peers. It is considered a significant tool in language classes, especially with low proficient learners. For instance, Safa and Rozati (2017) conducted a study in Iran to demonstrate the impact of scaffolding and non-scaffolding strategies on the EFL learners' listening comprehension development. Ninety intermediate EFL learners were randomly selected and divided into two experimental groups. The findings of the study revealed a positive impact of teacher scaffolding and peer scaffolding in listening class. Moreover, Jin (2002) conducted an experimental study on forty-six high school students in Korea. The students were divided into twenty-three students in each group. Within the treatment of one month, the teacher used scaffolding for implementing metacognitive listening strategies to the experimental group. The results revealed that students in the experimental group outperformed the students in the control group.

Additionally, scaffolding plays a vital role in online learning too. Cho and Cho (2016) have concluded that online instructors' conscious and effortful use of scaffolding strategies is an important factor in promoting interactions in online courses. Scale development method was implemented in the study. The purpose of their research was to develop a scale assessing online instructors' use of scaffolding strategies to promote interactions. Later, the factor analysis revealed that the new scale with scaffolding strategies promoted interactions with sound validity and reliability. In another study, Ann et al. (2009) also compared different interaction patterns between teacher and students in a learning environment where the researchers analyzed the data using both qualitative and quantitative paradigms in a mixed-study design. As a result, it was revealed that students were not often responsive in online teaching. Furthermore, Picard and Velautham (2016) also developed online materials to scaffold listening practices for the adults in a focused group. They engaged the learners in top-down and bottom-up approaches alongside cognitive and metacognitive strategies. The scaffolding through online materials was

found effective in learning a language. Gopang et al. (2023) also used the technique of scaffolding while employing the project-based learning method with BS English students at a public university in Pakistan. The researchers used a mixed method approach to obtain the data. Questionnaires and reflections were used as data collection instruments in this study. The results revealed an unavoidable need for scaffolding technique, especially when administering novice teaching methods with the students. Thus, the present study also aimed to implement scaffolding techniques with low achievers in online teaching in EFL context.

Recently, Alghamdy (2024) observed the negative impact for not implying the scaffolding techniques in language learning. The scholar pointed out that teachers only employ teaching-supporting practices at lower levels in the ZPD. The results highlighted that some tactics, including focusing on fixing mistakes during the planning phase before executing the lesson, are being used more frequently. The findings also indicated an increase in the adoption of certain tactics by professors, such as promoting constant classroom discussion without giving students the right answers prior to class talks. Instead of using these strategies, teachers could have used scaffolding strategies for better outcome.

In the local context, mixed-ability classroom is another challenge, which could be minimized with scaffolding technique. Chea and Kuon (2024) conducted a study in Cambodia where the teachers faced numerous difficulties when teaching English language lessons to students of varying aptitude levels. Nevertheless, scaffolding techniques have been acknowledged for their capacity to help educators overcoming these obstacles.

4.3 Interactive Multimedia Platforms in Scaffolding Listening Skills

Interactive multimedia refers to forums that use various types of media, such as text, audio, video, and graphics, to create engaging and interactive learning experiences (Clark & Mayer, 2016). Research indicates that interactive multimedia platforms can be a valuable source for enhancing learners' listening skills. Meskill and Anthony (2010) suggest that multimedia platforms provide an interactive platform for learners where they exchange ideas, ask questions and provide

feedback to one another. By participating in collaborative activities, learners develop listening skills and a scaffolding comprehension process. In another research by Wang et al. (2018) found that interactive multimedia platforms integrating authentic materials such as documentaries significantly improve learners' listening skills. Moreover, Putri et al. (2024) conducted a study on fifty-three students studying English literature at the state university in North Sumatera. They paired sample t-test and independent t-test for data analysis. The result of their study indicated that multimedia featuring Moodle and Thinklink help in increasing students' listening comprehension. Furthermore, Wang and Smith (2017) discuss the effectiveness of interactive multimedia platforms in enhancing listening comprehension skills among second language learners. The study revealed that learners who were taught in multimedia-rich contexts improved their ability to understand spoken language. However, other research studies have suggested limitations and challenges associated with the use of Interactive Multimedia platforms. For example, a study by Zhang and Barbar (2015) concluded that multimedia platforms may hinder students' motivation and engagement. Similarly, Mayer and Moreno (2003) argue that complex multimedia presentations may result in no cognitive response at the learners' mind.

5.0 Methodology

This study followed a qualitative research paradigm because as stated by Creswell and Creswell (2017), "... it focuses on the process that is occurring as well as the product or outcome" (p. 180). Under qualitative research design, action research design was employed because Burns (2009) expressed that action research is one of the best choices for teacher researchers to conduct classroom research. However, it is a very rigorous process as it works in four phases of a cycle: reflect, plan, act, observe, and then reflect to continue through the cycle (Dickens & Watkins, 1999), therefore, the action plan was followed in these stages (Kolb, 1984). This cycle was used specifically because it reflects on everyday experience observed in a classroom. Khurram (2023) also used the action research under the similar settings.

The process was initiated with teacher reflections as one of the researchers acted as the participant

in the study as well, including one female and three male students enrolled in an undergraduate program at a public university in Karachi, Pakistan. Participants of the study were selected using purposive sampling technique. The students had exposure to the English language, studying as ESL/EFL language for almost twelve years in academic settings. Initially, there were around thirty-four students enrolled in the batch, but only twelve were regular students in the online sessions; therefore, a listening test of pre-intermediate level was conducted with them to identify the low-scoring students from the evaluation. Total five students got lesser grades and were struggling using listening skills. Among five students, only three agreed to take part in the study.

Considering the pre-intermediate level of undergraduate students, the test was selected from IELTS practice listening tests available on the British Council's website. The tests were only used to reach the struggling learners, therefore, the students were evaluated on a grading scale and no numerical measurements were used to maintain the qualitative approach.

The data were collected from students' feedback and the teacher's researcher diary. Students' learning and development was reflected through feedback provided by students via email at the end of every class. The teachers' scaffolding was analysed through a reflective cycle and researcher diary using content analysis, however, students' feedback was analysed using thematic coding. Engin (2011) called the use of researcher diary as 'my expert other', therefore, it was also used for classroom observations. Moreover, ethical issues were considered by priorly informing the participants about the data collection procedure and taking the signed consents from them. Pseudo names were used to hide the identity of participants in the analysis. Data were gathered over the course of two weeks in four sessions, each lasting 40 minutes in virtual class.

6.0 Data Analysis

For data analysis, the feedback was coded thematically to understand the impact of scaffolding on learners and the challenges that they faced. While the teacher was very excited to teach listening, the students were observed to be absolutely demotivated. It was noticed that the strength of the class suddenly declined and there were only a few students in listening classes. Some

of them had internet connectivity issues due to which they could not join the class. Furthermore, the differences were noticed among students' competency in listening. Firstly, some students were not able to process the pace of the speakers due to unfamiliarity with English accents. It was detected when one student commented that "The voice is too quick, I cannot understand anything" (BJ). With the help of students' feedback and teacher's notes, it was planned to decrease the speed of the audio, less from the regular voice, so that students can get comfortable and familiar with the accent.

Secondly, the students were not aware of the tone and speech style which made it difficult for them to identify the main ideas shared by the speaker. Due to this reason, another student commented: "I do not know what to focus on in two minutes of audio" (MH). During the regular classes, the teacher used scaffolding as a teaching strategies to these learners. It was then taught to the students in the next session to locate the main idea through the tone of the speaker. However, educating them about intonation and stress patterns became challenging for the teacher because some students were completely novel to the English accents. So, I had to modify my lesson plan and devote some time to teaching speeches styles and tone.

Thirdly, the students did not have enough range of vocabulary as per the required level of expected proficiency to comprehend content. So, at this point, the student wrote: '*Meri vocabulary theek nahi hai, mujhe angreezi ke alfaaz samjh nahi aate* (I don't have good vocabulary, I lack proficiency in English vocabulary)' (RA). At this point, a frustration was reflected on the teacher's part in the field notes because I had to buckle up and train the students from the scratch to make them able to cope up with the level of degree they were enrolled in. I decided not to level down the content rather decided to teach students how to deduce the meaning of difficult words from the context cues.

After these teacher interventions, the students' feedback turned positive. Firstly, teacher scaffolding helped students in learning the skill as a student wrote: "*Teacher ke samjhane se meri activity sahi ho gayi* (I performed well with teachers' help)" (MH). It shows that weak students need extra help from teachers to acquire the skills in a classroom context. In addition to that, I used technique of

scaffolding with learners in before-during-after listening strategies. I told them that we always have to get prepared before listening to the test, so that we already have the purpose in mind. It will help us infer the meaning of the content. Similarly, during-listening activities are also very important to perform. Without these strategies, the comprehension will likely fail.

In the same sense, the listener's job does not end with the speaker's speech. The listener still has to perform some activities even after the completion of audio content to comprehend better. I taught them different note-taking strategies which also helped them in memorizing and referring back to the details. But all of these strategies were taught to them for the activities with recorded audios. However, when I asked the students to perform listening during the class presentations, they found it more convenient because they were allowed to ask questions for clarification in one-to-one interactions. At this point, they also evaluated the speech with the help of kinesics expressions and body language. I also asked the students to practice listening with standard accents (like, British and American) outside the class. I assigned them a few home tasks on weekends as well which assisted them in guided learning. Birjandi and Jazebi (2014) highlighted the significance of timely fading of the teacher scaffolding. In the same way, I slowly stopped helping them and motivated them to become independent learners. Meanwhile, they developed the sense of peer-scaffolding on their own.

After two sessions on listening and scaffolding, the students performed very well with the listening activities. They mentioned it in the feedback that they asked the high-achievers to share the strategies they used to comprehend the listening content. This is one of the advantages of doing group activities in the class where students get a chance to collaborate during peer-scaffolding as well. Moreover, they also mentioned how scaffolding helped them comprehend the content. This way, it can be noticed that scaffolding helped the low-achievers to become proficient learners. Besides this, Walker (2014) pointed out that teaching listening is not an easy task, and teacher motivation has a significant impact on student motivation to participate in class activities. So, I also had to be vigilant and monitor both teaching and students' comprehension strategies simultaneously. Also, I was very conscious about

selecting the authentic listening tasks which require a lot of labour. For this reason, the teachers' participation is considered a key to scaffolding learners.

7.0 Findings

Listening is an essential skill to learn a language. Without listening, the idea of oral communication is incomplete. It needs to be taught formally because it is learnt in a natural setting (Goh, 2010). But, in the EFL context, learners do not get listening opportunities in a natural setting, so its appropriate teaching becomes significant. Therefore, the teachers should engage students in listening strategies in EFL classes. However, the students need scaffolding to become strategic and skilled listeners.

In Pakistan, the educational institutions have insufficient resources, especially in public sectors. Due to this reason, both the teachers and students suffer from various skills and lack behind in many ways as compared to the people affiliated with private institutions. Likewise, teaching of listening requires properly furnished audio-visual rooms. Unfortunately, it becomes almost impossible to teach listening in the local context. Therefore, listening is the most neglected language skill in Pakistan. However, due to Covid-19 pandemic, there was a sudden shift to virtual teaching. So, this facility became readily available in online teaching. Many resources were able to teach listening like audio-visual sources, internet, and many more.

To sum up, a huge difference is observed in the performances of students after employing scaffolding in listening class. Lastly, it is assumed that teaching and scaffolding listening strategies is easier in online classes as compared to physical classes. Thus, it is recommended to ESL/EFL teachers to consider scaffolding as a useful technique for language teaching. The implications of the study will be seen in English language teaching in particular.

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